

Final Report

Einfluss von Sulfiden und Sauerstoff auf die Bildung und Stabilität von Korrosionsschutzschichten auf Bewehrungsstahl in alkaliaktivierten Betonen

Influence of Sulfide and Oxygen on the Formation and Stability of Corrosion Protection Layers on Reinforcing Steel in Alkali-Activated Concretes

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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2 Summary

To obtain a better understanding of the fundamental processes at the steel–concrete interface in materials with ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS), the electrochemical behaviour of steel in synthetic pore solutions of different GGBFS-containing cements were examined. Specifically, the study investigated the impact of reduced sulfur species (HS^- , S_n^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, SO_3^{2-}) on the corrosion and electrochemical properties, including the critical chloride threshold, of GGBFS-containing systems. Hardened cement pastes containing GGBFS were characterized to evaluate their phase composition and pore solutions were extracted and analysed using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) and ion chromatography (IC). Based on the results, synthetic pore solutions were formulated to approximate the chemical environment in the hydrated systems. Electrochemical characterization of carbon steel was then performed in these synthetic solutions under both anoxic and oxic conditions to assess its behaviour in chloride-free and in chloride-containing environments. Under anoxic, chloride-

free conditions, carbon steel in CEM I pore solution develops passivity, indicated by increasing open circuit potential (OCP) and polarization resistance (R_p), reflecting conventional iron oxide/hydroxide film (“passive layer”) formation. Conversely, steel in all sulfide-containing solutions maintains persistently negative OCPs (-550 to -700 mV vs. Ag/AgCl) and low apparent R_p (3 – 50 $\text{k}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$). These reduced R_p are dominated by sulfur redox reactions rather than iron dissolution, i.e., dissolved sulfide oxidation increases current response and artificially lowers polarisation resistance. Steel in CEM I pore solutions gradually develops a protective oxide film under oxygen-free conditions but can deteriorate as chlorides accumulate. In contrast, sulfide-rich systems sustain a reducing environment and yield consistent electrochemical responses regardless of chloride level. When oxygen is introduced, steel in CEM I solution forms robust passive layers that resist corrosion initiation until the chloride concentration reaches ~ 3 M, whereas reduced sulfur species consume dissolved oxygen and fundamentally alter steel corrosion mechanisms by consuming dissolved oxygen, effectively maintaining anoxic conditions even under oxygen access. This oxygen depletion prevents conventional passive film formation while simultaneously protecting against chloride-induced corrosion until all reduced sulfur species are completely oxidised. Investigations of surface layer formation and electrolyte resistance in mortar samples under both free and limited oxygen access showed that oxygen availability and binder composition control surface layer development, with E_{corr} , R_p and bulk electrolyte resistance (R_e) evolving over months in line with drying and oxygen ingress. Complementary corrosion studies on steel in both standard cement-based, GGBFS-containing mortars and alkali-activated slag (AAS) mortars under 5 % NaCl exposure showed that the different pore structures and permeabilities influence the penetration behaviour, so that a planned depassivation by diffusion could not be achieved within the project duration. Taken together, the project results challenge the validity of traditional electrochemical corrosion assessment methods and underscore the need for modified evaluation criteria for sustainable GGBFS-containing concrete systems.

Deutsch: Um ein besseres Verständnis der Vorgänge an der Grenzfläche Stahl–Beton in hüttensandhaltigen Materialien zu erhalten, wurde das elektrochemische Verhalten von Bewehrungsstahl in synthetischen Porenlösungen verschiedener Zemente analysiert. Im Mittelpunkt stand der Einfluss reduzierter Schwefelspezies (HS^- , S_n^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, SO_3^{2-}) auf das Korrosionsverhalten und die elektrochemischen Eigenschaften dieser Systeme, inkl. der Identifikation der kritischen Chloridkonzentration, die zur Depassivierung des Stahls führt. Zementsteine mit Hüttensand (HÜS) wurden charakterisiert und ihre Porenlösungen mittels ICP-OES und IC analysiert. Auf Basis dieser Daten und publizierter Literatur wurden synthetische

Porenlösungen formuliert, die den chemischen Bedingungen der hydratisierten Systeme (angenähert) entsprechen. Anschließend erfolgte die elektrochemische Charakterisierung von Stahl in diesen Lösungen unter anoxischen und oxischen Bedingungen zur Bewertung des Korrosionsverhaltens in chloridfreien und in chloridhaltigen Medien. Unter anoxischen, chloridfreien Bedingungen entwickelt Stahl in CEM I-Porenlösung allmählich Passivität, erkennbar an ansteigendem Ruhepotential und Polarisationswiderstand (R_p), was der typischen Bildung von Eisenoxid-/Hydroxidschichten („Passivschicht“) entspricht. Im Gegensatz dazu wurden in allen sulfidhaltigen Lösungen dauerhaft negative Ruhepotentialen (-550 bis -700 mV vs. Ag/AgCl) und niedrige scheinbare R_p ($3-50$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$) gemessen, die von Redoxreaktionen der Schwefelspezies bestimmt werden. Bei Zutritt von Sauerstoff bilden CEM I-Systeme robuste Passivschichten, die Chloridkonzentrationen bis etwa 3 M widerstehen, während reduzierte Schwefelspezies gelösten Sauerstoff verbrauchen und so eine anoxische Umgebung aufrechterhalten. Erst wenn alle Sulfidspezies oxidiert sind, kann chloridinduzierte Korrosion einsetzen. Untersuchungen der Deckschichtbildung und des Elektrolytwiderstands in Mörtelproben zeigten sowohl unter freiem als auch unter eingeschränktem Sauerstoffzugang, dass die Sauerstoffverfügbarkeit und die Bindemittelzusammensetzung die Entwicklung der Deckschicht bestimmen, wobei sich E_{corr} , R_p und der Elektrolytwiderstand (R_e) über Monate hinweg in Abhängigkeit von der Trocknung und dem Sauerstoffeintritt entwickeln. Ergänzende Korrosionsstudien an Stahl in zementbasierten, HÜS-haltigen Standardmörteln und AAS-Mörteln unter 5 %iger NaCl-Belastung zeigten, dass die unterschiedlichen Porenstrukturen und Permeabilitäten das Eindringverhalten stark beeinflussen, so dass eine geplante Depassivierung durch Diffusion innerhalb des Projektzeitraums nicht erreicht werden konnte. Die Projektergebnisse stellen traditionelle elektrochemische Bewertungsmethoden infrage und zeigen die Notwendigkeit angepasster Bewertungskriterien für nachhaltige, HÜS-haltige Betonsysteme auf.

3 Progress Report

Introduction

Reinforced concrete is the backbone of modern infrastructure globally, *inter alia* because of its versatility and cost-effectiveness. However, the long-term performance and safety of reinforced concrete structures are dependent on the durability of the embedded steel reinforcement [1]. Among the supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) employed in cement and concrete, ground granulated blast-furnace slag (GGBFS) is particularly common, and it has become increasingly popular in recent years due to its potential to reduce CO₂ emissions related to cement production and use, including through use in alkali-activated materials (AAMs). During the hydration of cements with GGBFS, reduced sulfur species, particularly hydrogen

sulfide ions (HS^-), are released into the pore solution of the cements [2, 3]. This leads to reducing conditions (low redox potential) in the pore solution, with important consequences for the corrosion behaviour of reinforcing steel [7, 8].

To obtain a better understanding of the fundamental processes occurring at the steel–concrete interface and the behaviour of steel reinforcement in cementitious materials with GGBFS, this project investigated the electrochemical behaviour of steel in synthetic pore solutions simulating GGBFS-containing cementitious systems, and the electrochemical response of steel rebars in mortars produced with such cements exposed to relevant conditions.

Analyses of pore solutions and synthetic solutions

A total of eight pastes (**Table 1**) were designed, prepared and characterized at BAM. X-ray diffraction and TGA/DTG showed that the alkali-activated slag (AAS 100) and GGBFS/fly ash (FA) blends (AAS 90, AAS 75) form C-(N-)A-S-H gel with hydrotalcite-type phases. The hybrid cement (CEM III/C + activator) contained ettringite and monosulfate, while CEM III/B and CEM III/C contained ettringite and hemicarbonate.

Table 1. Compositions of the cement pastes

ID	Solid starting materials	Na ₂ O/s	M _s	w/b
AAS 100	GGBFS	3.0 %	0.60	0.40
AAS 90	90 % GGBFS + 10 % FA	3.8 %	0.47	0.40
AAS 75	75 % GGBFS + 25 % FA	3.5 %	0.39	0.40
AAS 50	50 % GGBFS + 50 % FA	2.7 %	0.33	0.40
CEM III/C+Act.	96 % CEM III/C + 4 % Na ₂ SO ₄	-	-	0.40
CEM III/C	CEM III/C	-	-	0.40
CEM III/B	CEM III/B	-	-	0.40
CEM I	CEM I	-	-	0.40

Pore solution extraction was performed under an argon gas in a purpose-built expression cell [4] to obtain 10–25 mL of solution per specimen for subsequent analyses of pH, electrical conductivity, redox potential, sulfate concentration, and elemental composition by ion chromatography and ICP-OES at RWTH Aachen University. The redox potentials exhibited a clear dependence on GGBFS content (**Figure 1**). CEM I solutions remained mildly oxidising, with potentials from +8 mV to +20 mV, whereas AAS 100, AAS 90, and AAS 75 showed strongly reducing conditions around –500 mV, reflecting the dissolution of sulfide species released from the slag during hydration. Sulfate concentrations varied widely: they were highest in CEM III/C + activator at 175–210 mM, very low in CEM III B and CEM III C at under 5 mM, and intermediate in the alkali-activated systems at 35–70 mM throughout hydration. These findings

underscore the role of reduced sulfur from GGBFS in creating persistently reducing pore environments and carry significant implications for the corrosion resistance of steel reinforcement in sustainable cement formulations.

In order to perform electrochemical measurements, seven synthetic pore solutions were designed and prepared, using analytical-grade reagents (NaOH, Ca(OH)₂, Na₂SO₄, NaCl, Na₂S·xH₂O), to approximate the cement pore solutions for subsequent measurements. Solutions were prepared in a continuously argon-purged glovebox using deionized water deaerated with nitrogen gas (dissolved oxygen < 0.2 ppm) to maintain oxygen-free conditions. The specific compositions representing various binder chemistries are detailed in **Table 2**.

Figure 1. Redox potentials of the expressed pore solutions of the cement pastes vs. the GGBFS fraction of the solid binders.

Table 2. Chemical composition of the solutions

ID	Na ⁺ (mM)	Ca ²⁺ (mM)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mM)	HS ⁻ (mM)
AAS 100	1500	0.5	50	350
AAS 90	1400	0.5	50	300
AAS 75	1200	0.5	50	200
AAS 50	800	0.5	50	50
CEM III+Act.	1000	0.5	200	100
CEM III	100	0.5	2	10
CEM I	550	1	20	0

Electrochemical behaviour and surface layer formation in synthetic pore solutions

Electrochemical measurements were carried out at (25 ± 2) °C using a Gamry Interface 1010E potentiostat/galvanostat/ZRA. A standard three-electrode cell employed a S235 (JRG2 1.0038) steel disk as the working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode, and a Ag/AgCl/KCl_{sat.} reference electrode. Before electrochemical testing, specimens were cleaned with acetone and isopropyl alcohol to remove surface contaminants and ensure a consistent initial condition. For each set of conditions, at least three independent steel specimens were tested. Before each sequence, specimens were held at open circuit for 20 minutes to stabilise

the steel–solution interface. For experiments requiring oxygen-free conditions, anoxic conditions were preserved by continuously purging the cell headspace with high-purity nitrogen gas. The steel condition was monitored over 14 days by measuring open circuit potential (OCP) and polarization resistance [R_p ; using the linear polarization (LPR) technique] to assess passivity and corrosion kinetics. At each interval, the OCP was recorded continuously for 10 minutes and averaged over the final 50 seconds to obtain a stable potential representative of the steel–solution interface. LPR measurements applied a ± 5 mV perturbation around the OCP at 0.167 mV/s, and the slope of the resulting potential–current plot yielded the polarization resistance ($R_p = \Delta E/\Delta I$). R_p is inversely proportional to corrosion rate under Tafel kinetics and, thus, provides a rapid, minimally invasive metric of passive film integrity.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of OCP and R_p for steel immersed in sulfide-rich, chloride-free synthetic pore solutions under anoxic, highly alkaline conditions over 14 days. Steel specimens in the CEM I synthetic pore solution exhibited a gradual shift toward more noble potentials, with OCP rising from -250 mV to -150 mV and R_p increasing from ~ 70 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ to ~ 250 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$. This behavior reflects the progressive stabilisation of a passive film through iron oxidation and oxide/hydroxide layer development in the absence of reduced sulfur species. In contrast, all steel specimens immersed in GGBFS-containing solutions (CEM III, CEM III+Act., AAS 50, AAS 75, AAS 90, AAS 100) maintained persistently negative OCP values (-550 to -700 mV) and low R_p values (3 – 50 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$), indicating that reduced sulfur species drove the environment into a highly reduced state.

Figure 2. Evolution of (a) OCP and (b) R_p for steel immersed in sulfide-rich, chloride-free synthetic pore solutions under anoxic, highly alkaline conditions over 14 days.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was applied to verify the results for some of the solutions [5]. The electrical equivalent circuit (EEC) to fit the data required constant phase

elements to achieve adequate fitting. The obtained resistance values representing the steel–solution interface (for the EEC, see [5]) were in the range approx. 30–80 k Ω ·cm² for AAS 50, AAS 75 and AAS 100, and generally of the order of magnitude but slightly higher for CEM III, generally confirming the LPR measurements.

Importantly, the obtained R_p values in the sulfide-containing solutions do not correspond solely to the Fe/Fe²⁺ redox couple but rather involve multiple redox reactions of sulfur species at the steel surface [7, 8]. Because LPR measures the total current response to a small potential perturbation, oxidation of reduced sulfur species increases current (ΔI) for a given ΔE , lowering the apparent polarization resistance. Thus, the low R_p observed in these sulfide-rich systems represents an “apparent” resistance governed by reduced sulfur species oxidation kinetics rather than pure iron dissolution.

Surface layer formation and electrolyte resistance in mortar samples

A set of 52 cylindrical mortar specimens, each containing a sand-blasted S235 steel working electrode in a three-electrode setup, was tested under two curing regimes. In the “Air” series, specimens were demolded after three days, had top and bottom faces sealed to allow oxygen ingress only from the lateral surface, and were stored at 20 °C/50 % RH. In the “Formwork” series, only the bottom plate was removed after three days, leaving the circular formwork intact to restrict oxygen access. Over 385 days, open-circuit potential (E_{corr}) and R_p were recorded regularly, and EIS measurements made. At the end of this period, selected specimens underwent anodic polarization, and the steel was visually inspected after splitting the mortar.

Passivation was interpreted not as reaching a fixed threshold but as gradual protective-layer formation, signaled by a positive shift of E_{corr} (as oxygen-consuming reactions subside) and a concurrent rise of R_p (increased charge-transfer resistance). In the “Air” series, standard and hybrid cements exceeded 0 mV_{SHE} within weeks with $R_p > 1000$ k Ω ·cm². GGBFS-rich AAMs (AAS100/AAS90) reached $E_{\text{corr}} > 0$ mV_{SHE} in 10–20 days and R_p of 500–700 k Ω ·cm² (**Figure 3**). FA-rich AAMs (AAS75/AAS50) maintained E_{corr} below –700 mV_{SHE} for 30–70 days, only surpassing 0 mV_{SHE} after 80–160 days, and kept $R_p < 100$ k Ω ·cm² until 70–110 days before rising toward 1000 k Ω ·cm². Early polarization (36–94 days) of GGBFS-rich AAMs showed current peaks at 160–200 mV_{SHE}, likely due to oxidation of residual sulfide species, that vanished by ≥ 270 days; late-tested FA-rich AAMs displayed lower currents and minimal peaks, indicating more mature surface stabilization.

Under the oxygen-restricted “Formwork” regime, steel passivation proceeded more slowly: standard cements with GGBFS never exceeded $R_p \sim 700$ k Ω ·cm², and most AAMs stayed below ~ 400 k Ω ·cm². AAMs held E_{corr} beneath –700 mV_{SHE} for 30–80 days, only rising to ~ 150

mV_{SHE} after 100–150 days (with four specimens delayed further). Anodic polarization at 204–351 days again showed current peaks around 200–250 mV_{SHE} in some AAMs but, lacking any visible corrosion, these peaks instead reflect ongoing pore-solution redox reactions (e.g., HS^- oxidation) rather than active degradation.

Figure 3. E_{corr} and R_p in the AAS binders in the series “Air” (left) and “Formwork” (right).

After 385 days, visual inspection including 3D scanning at 0.05 mm resolution revealed only slight discoloration and no significant corrosion, confirming a passive, protective condition. Electrolyte resistance (R_e , from EIS at 100–1000 Hz) increased over time in both regimes but rose more slowly and to lower levels under “Formwork” conditions. Within the standard cements, binders with higher GGBFS content showed the highest R_e , while in AAMs R_e increased with higher FA content, especially in the longer-monitored “Air” series. Moisture retention in formwork samples also depressed R_e , underscoring that both microstructural development and water content govern electrolyte resistance.

All mortars achieved passivation of embedded steel, evidenced by rising E_{corr} and R_p , with no material loss, but its timing and rate depend on oxygen availability and drying. Fixed E_{corr} or R_p

thresholds are insufficient for universal assessment, particularly in novel binder systems. A time-resolved, context-sensitive interpretation of electrochemical data, thus accounting for environmental factors, seems essential for accurately evaluating steel passivation in various cementitious materials.

Critical chloride concentration in solution in synthetic pore solutions

To determine the critical chloride concentration required to initiate corrosion, steel specimens were pre-treated in chloride-free synthetic pore solutions for 10 days under exclusion of oxygen to allow the formation of a stable surface layer. Following pre-treatment, two distinct conditions were maintained: anoxic experiments with continuous nitrogen purging throughout the procedure, and oxic experiments where the cell was exposed to oxygen after pre-treatment. The Cl^- concentration in the solutions was increased stepwise by addition of NaCl. At each chloride level, after an equilibration period of at least 2 hours, OCP were recorded using a 10-minute averaging method, followed by linear polarization resistance (LPR) measurements (± 5 mV versus OCP at 0.167 mV/s). NaCl additions continued until corrosion initiation, indicated by a drop of OCP and/or a significant decrease of R_p , was observed.

Figure 4 shows the evolution of OCP and R_p for steel immersed in synthetic pore solutions as a function of chloride concentration under anoxic conditions. The steel specimens exhibited markedly different OCP and R_p responses depending on the solution composition. In CEM I solutions, the initial OCP stabilised at approximately -140 mV in the chloride-free medium and remained approximately constant until the chloride concentration reached 0.6 M. Beyond this threshold, the OCP underwent a continuous negative shift, eventually reaching -400 mV at 4 M Cl^- . In contrast, all steel specimens in sulfide-containing solutions displayed substantially more negative initial potentials that changed only marginally with increasing chloride content. Notably, the steel in the CEM III solution began at -500 mV and decreased monotonically to -635 mV at 4 M Cl^- without the abrupt OCP drops characteristic of passive film breakdown. Correspondingly, R_p for steels in sulfide-containing synthetic pore solutions remained in the narrow range of 20–50 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ across the entire chloride range, whereas CEM I exhibited an initial R_p of ~ 160 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ that declined sharply beyond 0.6 M Cl^- before levelling off at ~ 50 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ at chloride concentrations ≥ 1.5 M.

It is concluded that the observed behavior of the steel in the sulfide-containing solutions was caused by the fact that the strongly reducing conditions did not allow the cathodic reaction that would be required for stable pit formation to occur and, thus, inhibited corrosion initiation. In the CEM I solution, the conditions were less reducing and trace amounts of oxygen were present so that corrosion initiation was possible, though the behaviour of the steel differed from

“normal” (*i.e.*, oxic) conditions in that the decrease of OCP and R_p occurred gradually rather than abrupt.

Figure 4. Evolution of (a) OCP and (b) R_p for steel immersed in synthetic pore solutions as a function of chloride concentration in an anoxic condition.

Figures 5 and 6 show the evolution of OCP and R_p for steel in synthetic pore solutions during pre-treatment and subsequent access of oxygen, at different chloride concentrations. The access of oxygen profoundly influenced both OCP and R_p , underscoring the dual role of oxygen in passive film formation and deterioration under chloride-induced corrosion. Before chloride addition, steel in the CEM I solution exhibited an OCP of approximately -130 mV and a high R_p of around 180 $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$. In comparison, CEM III stabilised at -340 mV ($R_p \approx 12$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$), AAS 50 at -510 mV ($R_p \approx 14$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$), AAS 75 at -580 mV ($R_p \approx 6$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$), AAS 90 at -610 mV ($R_p \approx 10$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$), and AAS 100 at -610 mV ($R_p \approx 10$ $k\Omega \cdot cm^2$).

Figure 5. Evolution of OCP for steel immersed in synthetic pore solutions with oxygen access, at different chloride concentrations.

Figure 6. Evolution of R_p for steel immersed in synthetic pore solutions with oxygen access, at different chloride concentrations.

Upon the first chloride increment to 0.2 M, steel in CEM III solution experienced an instantaneous decrease of R_p to $\sim 1 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ accompanied by a 130-mV drop of OCP, indicating rapid breakdown of its passive layer. Subsequent chloride additions maintained CEM III in the active corrosion regime ($R_p \approx 0.5\text{--}1 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$). CEM I preserved both noble potentials and $R_p > 90 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ until the Cl^- concentration reached 3 M; at 4 M Cl^- , its OCP declined sharply to -530 mV and R_p fell to $\sim 2 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$, defining its critical chloride threshold. Steel in the AAS solutions showed largely stable OCP and R_p values across the entire chloride range, with no sudden shifts detected.

The differing behaviours observed for anoxic and oxic conditions illuminate fundamental mechanisms governing steel corrosion in alkaline cement environments. The anoxic results demonstrate that chloride ions can progressively degrade an incomplete passive film on steel in CEM I solutions, as indicated by continuous negative OCP shifts; however, without dissolved oxygen, the cathodic reaction is suppressed and polarization resistance remains elevated, yielding slow corrosion kinetics. Under oxic conditions, oxygen serves a dual function. It is crucial for the initial formation of the passive film, particularly at high pH levels where the film becomes thicker and more protective. However, it also promotes rapid breakdown of the passive film once the chloride concentration exceeds the critical threshold. Sulfide in solutions simulating GGBFS-containing cements scavenged dissolved oxygen, effectively maintaining anoxic corrosion behaviour even when cells were air-exposed, with only the low-sulfide (10 mM HS^-) CEM III system permitting sufficient oxygen uptake to initiate chloride-induced corrosion already at very low Cl^- concentration (0.2 M). In all other sulfide-rich media, reduced sulfur species acted as oxygen scavengers, preventing cathodic oxygen reduction, stabilising OCP, and

preserving polarization resistance across the full chloride range up to 4 M, underscoring the complex interplay between surface layer chemistry, chloride concentration, and oxygen availability in determining steel corrosion thresholds in alkaline pore-solution environments.

Corrosion studies on steel in alkali-activated concretes

48 mortar specimens, each with three sand-blasted S235 steel bars (\varnothing 8 mm) at “Top,” “Middle,” and “Bottom” heights and 110 mm free length starting 20 mm from the specimen edges, were removed from the moulds after 3 days, cured at 20 °C in damp conditions for 7 days, and then stored at 20 °C/50 % RH. The multi-bar setup enabled extended monitoring of one bar post-depassivation while determining the critical chloride threshold (c_{crit}) on another. After the passivation period (up to several months), a basin for 5 % NaCl solution was applied over a ~15 mm mortar cover, that was ground to that level shortly before preparation. A MnO_2 reference electrode was coupled with ultrasonic gel and sealed under plastic foil; all other faces were epoxy-sealed to prevent leaks. Steel OCP was recorded for several days to confirm passivation, then a 5 % NaCl solution was applied and potentials logged every 30 minutes, using a ≥ 200 mV drop to mark depassivation. As most specimens remained passive for months, the testing was paused. The mortar cover was ground back to ~5 mm, and the NaCl basins were reduced in size so that the penetration area was concentrated on the middle areas of the steel lengths, as some removed steels showed traces of crevice corrosion at the steel ends (without potential drop and without cross-section loss (**Figure 7**)). Due to the lack of depassivation of the steels, a second setup with variation of the oxygenation of the cathode, as planned in the proposal, was not employed.

Figure 7. Specimen setup before (left) and after (right) reducing the mortar cover and reattachment of the basin

Figure 8. Compilation of the results with CEMIII/B-1 as an example.

Chloride ingress depended strongly on the pore structures. Initial capillary suction can rapidly draw the NaCl solution into near-surface pores and depassivate any bar within that depth, an effect that is not representative of the critical chloride threshold. To distinguish suction-driven from diffusion-driven depassivation, bars that lost passivity within a few days were disregarded, while the specimens remained immersed until a second bar depassivated after ≥ 7 days. Once that later depassivation occurred, the exposure was stopped within 24 hours and the specimen was split open for visual inspection and potentiometric titration of chloride. Since most bars showed no potential drop over months, all remaining specimens were opened before the end of project to assess the steel surfaces and chloride distribution. Despite extensive data (potential curves, inspection photos and chloride concentrations of 176 mortar samples, see **Figure 8** as example), determining a reliable c_{crit} proved difficult, as diffusion-induced depassivation was rare.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that the presence of sulfide ions in GGBFS-containing cements fundamentally alters the electrochemical behaviour of steel reinforcement. According to conventional criteria for sulfide-free concretes [6], OCP values below -230 mV vs. Ag/AgCl indicate a high ($> 90\%$) corrosion probability, yet all specimens in sulfide-rich pore solutions exhibited OCPs more negative than this threshold without any visual evidence of corrosion. The observed electrochemical behaviour can be attributed to the oxidation processes of sulfide species; the measured R_p values do not solely represent the Fe/Fe²⁺ redox couple, but rather reflect a more complex system involving multiple redox reactions of sulfur species at the steel surface. This complexity requires careful analysis, as the conventional correlation between R_p and corrosion rate may not be applicable in these systems [7, 8]. Fundamentally, reduced sulfur species protect the steel by scavenging dissolved oxygen, thereby inhibiting the cathodic reaction necessary for chloride-induced attack. Any available oxygen would be locally consumed through sulfide oxidation, producing either partially oxidized species (*i.e.*, polysulfides, thiosulfate, or sulfite) and eventually fully oxidised species (*i.e.*, sulfate). Consequently, chloride-induced corrosion can only commence after sulfide in the pore solution has been virtually fully oxidised. Complementary mortar scale tests confirm that both E_{corr} and R_p rise over time in relation to oxygen availability and drying, while bulk electrolyte resistance (R_e) further reflects microstructural development and moisture content. Chloride exposure tests on steel in alkali-activated concretes underline that mortar cover, binder chemistry, and ingress mechanism impacts strongly depassivation. Due to capillary suction induced depassivation or absence of depassivation, corrosion thresholds could not be determined within the project timeframe.

Together, these findings highlight the need for a context-sensitive (particularly oxygen availability, chloride levels), time-resolved interpretation of E_{corr} , R_p , and R_e rather than fixed thresholds when evaluating the long-term durability of steel in sustainable, GGBFS-containing cementitious materials, and underscore the importance of integrating pore-solution chemistry, surface-layer formation, and concrete microstructure in corrosion-resistance design.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

Nikoonasab, A., Müller, T., & Gluth, G. J. G. (2024). Study of steel behavior in synthetic pore solutions of GGBFS-containing cements using EIS. In: *2024 International Workshop on Impedance Spectroscopy (IWIS)*, Chemnitz, Germany. IEEE, pp 44–48.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/IWIS63047.2024.10847235>

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

Licht, M., Nikoonasab, A., Gluth, G. J. G., & Raupach, M. (2023). Alkali-aktivierte Hütten-sandbetone – CO₂-reduzierte Bindemittel mit hohem Korrosionsschutzpotential. In: Claßen M, Hegger J, Matschei T, Raupach M (eds) *Beiträge zur 10. DAfStb-Jahrestagung mit 62.*

Forschungskolloquium. RWTH Aachen University, pp 233–238.
<https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2023-06676>

Nikoonasab, A., Müller, T., Licht, M., Raupach, M., & Gluth G. J. G. (2024). Sulfides in the pore solutions of GGBFS-containing concretes: influence on the corrosion of reinforcing steel. In: Rogge A, Meng B (eds) *11. Jahrestagung des DAfStb mit 63. Forschungskolloquium der BAM. Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)*, pp 55–59.

Gluth G. J. G., Sittner, J., Asante, B., Nikoonasab, A., & Ebell, G. (2025). Themenblock 1: Chemie der Bindemittel. *Beton* 75(4):129–131.